

MODERN STAGES OF THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL BASIS OF THE ACTIVITY OF THE INSTITUTE OF PUBLIC RECEPTION

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Abstract: The article describes the theoretical and methodological foundations and modern stages of the Institute of People's Receptions introduced by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev. The role of this institution in organizing open and effective communication with citizens, the mechanisms for solving citizens' problems, and the importance of improving interaction with state bodies are analyzed. Also, actual aspects of digital transformation and increasing community participation in the activities of public reception centers were considered.

Key words: People's lobby, open communication, state bodies, citizens, digital transformation, community participation, efficiency, methodological foundations.

The new system founded by the President Shavkat Mirziyoyev Miromonovich for active and open communication with the people, working with the appeals of individuals and legal entities - the Institute of People's Receptions, together with the new stage of development of the living traditions of the Uzbek philosophy of life and the school of national statehood in terms of ensuring social justice, will bring our country. It is no exaggeration to say that it is becoming a powerful tool for achieving strategic goals for comprehensive development. A council wedding is not widespread, there is a noble tradition in our people: before starting any work, it is done after consultation and careful consideration. In this, the opinion of young and old people is asked, they are analyzed, various opinions are listened to, and all relationships are taken into account. This method will certainly not fail to show the results of mutually agreed activities. Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his speech entitled "Continuous continuation of democratic reforms, creating a peaceful and peaceful, decent standard of living for our people - is a guarantee of sustainable development" at the 7th session of the Movement of Entrepreneurs and Businessmen - Liberal-Democratic Party of Uzbekistan the time has come. After that, the activities of the local leaders will be assessed based on the number of appeals received from the residents of the area they lead, their behavior among the people, and practical solutions to existing problems. In short, leaders are judged by the

people," he said. At the ceremony dedicated to the 24th anniversary of the adoption of our Constitution, the President announced 2017 as the year of dialogue with the people and the interests of the people in our country. a radical revision is necessary. In this regard, we need to constantly communicate with the population, introduce new mechanisms and effective methods of solving the problems that are bothering them," he said. Soon, our people are seeing the practical results of these ideas and initiatives in their lives.

Improving the efficiency of public receptions, processes of automation, increasing activity indicators and ensuring rational use of material resources is the most important factor for today's national development and development of the nation.

The Institute of Public Reception is an institution designed to facilitate the organization of state and public services and communication with the people. The main goal of this institute is to improve communication between citizens and state authorities and to help solve people's problems.

According to theoretical foundations, the institution of public reception is closely related to the following theoretical foundations:

- Open communication with citizens - its purpose is to establish effective communication with the people, to provide opportunities for citizens to speak, and to establish direct communication between state bodies and the population.
- Institutional model: The institutional model and principles that determine how public reception centers are established between government agencies and the public sector.
- Service Management: Theory of Customer Service and Service Quality Management. Effectively respond to the needs of citizens through these features.

Also, methodological bases, which include the following methodological bases for increasing the efficiency of public receptions:

Education and training Continuing education and professional development programs to improve the skills of employees and prepare them for effective work.

Management of systems and processes: methods of management, monitoring and evaluation of internal systems and processes of the People's Reception.

According to the use of technologies, it is envisaged to improve services through the use of innovative technologies, including electronic certificates, online applications and other digital tools.

The next stages are modern stages, according to which they include digital transformation, public participation, efficiency improvement, political and economic transformation. Let's define them one by one:

Digital transformation: Further development of communication with citizens through e-gov systems, mobile applications and online services.

Public participation: Active involvement of citizens in public administration processes, consideration of their opinions and suggestions.

Improving efficiency: Improving methods for improving service quality and solving problems quickly.

Political and economic changes: Changes in public policy and economic conditions mean updating services to meet the needs of the people.

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